

STRENGTHENING OF REINFORCED CONCRETE BEAMS USING CFRP AND GFRP COMPOSITES: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract: Concrete, steel, and masonry are widely used construction materials for structures such as residential buildings, office complexes, bridges, and power plants. Over time, these structures experience deterioration due to factors such as design inadequacies, material deficiencies, poor construction practices, and exposure to extreme loads. Many studies on the rehabilitation of damaged reinforced concrete (RC) structures focus on methods such as patch repair and the application of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) sheets for flexural, shear, and compressive strengthening. This research specifically examines the retrofitting of RC beams using glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) and carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) sheets. The study investigates the flexural behavior of M20, M40, and M60 grade RC beams strengthened with single, double, and triple layers of GFRP sheets. These beams were analyzed through ANSYS simulations and the results were compared with experimental data. Findings from the study indicate that retrofitting RC beams with GFRP and CFRP sheets significantly enhances their load-bearing capacity. Additionally, the beams exhibit increased deflections up to the yield point and reduced deflections beyond that point up to ultimate loading. Strengthened beams also show a notable reduction in crack width at all loading stages, along with a substantial delay in the initiation of the first crack.

Keywords: Reinforced concrete beams, retrofitting, GFRP sheets, CFRP sheets, flexural strengthening, load carrying capacity, crack width reduction, ANSYS modeling, composite materials, structural rehabilitation, fiber reinforced polymers, strengthening techniques, flexural behavior, RC beam deflection, experimental validation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Reinforced concrete (RC) remains one of the most widely used construction materials due to its strength, durability, and versatility in various structural applications such as residential buildings, commercial complexes, bridges, and power plants. However, over time, these structures are prone to deterioration caused by factors including design deficiencies, material degradation, poor workmanship, and exposure to harsh environmental conditions and excessive loading. Such deterioration compromises the structural integrity and safety of RC elements, necessitating effective rehabilitation and strengthening techniques to extend their service life.

Among various strengthening methods, the use of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites has gained significant attention due to their high

strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, ease of installation, and excellent mechanical properties. Carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) and glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) sheets are commonly applied for flexural, shear, and compressive strengthening of damaged or underperforming RC members. These materials provide a viable solution to enhance load-carrying capacity, improve structural performance, and delay crack propagation without significantly increasing the weight or thickness of the structure.

This research focuses on the retrofitting of RC beams using CFRP and GFRP sheets, with an emphasis on studying their flexural behaviour under varying grades of concrete (M20, M40, and M60) and different layers of GFRP application (single, double, and triple layers). The study integrates experimental testing and finite element analysis using ANSYS software to

provide a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of these composite materials in strengthening RC beams. The findings aim to contribute valuable insights into the structural enhancement potential of FRP composites, highlighting improvements in load capacity, deflection characteristics, and crack control.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Baiet et al. (2024) presented experimental study of the flexural performance of reinforced concrete (RC) beams externally bonded with hybrid fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) laminates made of carbon and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) fibers. Ten beam specimens were subjected to four-point bending tests, with a focus on assessing the effects of the stacking sequence and the elastic modulus of hybrid carbon-PET FRP laminates on the flexural performance of the strengthened beams. The failure modes, load-bearing capacities, displacement ductility of the specimens and strain distributions in the FRP laminates were examined and discussed.

Assad et al. (2024) presented investigate the flexural behaviour of externally strengthened RC beams with CFRP laminates and anchored at end with CFRP spike anchors. The results of anchored beams was compared with unanchored specimens in terms of load-deflection response, strain in the FRP laminates, and failure modes. Results showed that anchorage of CFRP laminates with CFRP splay anchors positively affected the flexural capacity of the specimens. An average increase in the load-carrying capacity of 19 % was portrayed in the anchored specimens compared to the unanchored specimen. Anchorage of FRP laminates resulted in the mitigation of debonding failure and thus, enhanced strain utilization in laminates

Makhloufet al. (2024) presented create composite sheets made of local natural fibers (jute fiber), which are cheap, environmentally friendly, and sustainable, and a new local epoxy resin (NOVO BOND EB) with high strength, especially in bonding to concrete, and low cost for use in shear strengthening of R.C. structures. In the experimental programme, the sheets were made from jute fiber-reinforced polymer (JFRP). Three samples of JFRP were tested to determine the mechanical properties of this material.

Mussaet al. (2024) presented investigate the behaviour of reinforced concrete (RC) beams strengthened by Carbon Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) under static and impact loads. A series of RC beams were tested and categorized into four groups, namely, unstrengthened RC beams (B1), RC beams strengthened with a CFRP longitudinal strip in the tension zone (B2), RC beams wrapped with

CFRP fabric (B3), and RC beams strengthened with a combination of both CFRP longitudinal strips and wraps (B4).

Shi et al. (2024) presented the effect of incorporating multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) in epoxy resin on the flexural behavior of reinforced concrete (RC) beams strengthened with basalt fiber-reinforced polymer (BFRP) sheets through four-point bending beam tests. Experimental results indicated that the flexural behavior was significantly improved by the MWCNT-modified epoxy.

Pour et al. (2024) presented the efficiency of different strengthening techniques to advance the flexural characteristics of reinforced concrete (RC) beams using glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) laminates, including externally bonded reinforcement (EBR), externally bonded reinforcement on grooves (EBROG), externally bonded reinforcement in grooves (EBRIG), and the near-surface mounted (NSM) system. A new NSM technique was also established using an anchorage rebar. Then, the effect of the NSM method with and without externally strengthening GFRP laminates was studied. Twelve RC beams (150 × 200 × 1500 mm) were manufactured and examined under a bending system. One specimen was designated as the control with no GFRP laminate.

Khan et al. (2024) presented data-driven estimation models, an extensive collection of experimental data on FRP-strengthened RC beams was compiled from the experimental studies. For the assessment of the accuracy of developed models, various statistical indicators were utilized. The machine learning (ML) based models were compared with empirical and conventional linear regression models to substantiate their superiority, providing evidence of enhanced performance. The GEP model demonstrated outstanding predictive performance with a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.98 for both the training and validation phases, accompanied by minimal mean absolute errors (MAE) of 4.08 and 5.39, respectively.

Zhang et al. (2024) presented a novel method of laying a composite layer of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) grid reinforced with engineering cementitious composite (ECC), designated as FGRE, and applied at the soffit of reinforced concrete (RC) beams to improve its flexural performance.

Gaberet al. (2024) presented experimental investigation on the improvement of the torsional resistance of reinforced concrete beams using fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) fabric. The experimental program outlines a comprehensive

analysis of the combined effects of shear and torsion on the torsional strengthening of four rectangular reinforced concrete beams with externally bonded glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) sheets.

Iyappanet al. (2024) presented the performance of Reinforced Concrete (RC) beams enhanced in shear using basalt fibre and glass fibre. After curing the beams were wrapped with fibres other than the conventional. All the 12 beams were tested under the same loading condition with the four point loading. The shear deficient RC beams do not have required shear reinforcement and hence they fail by shear first. FRP strengthening in the shear zones can increase the shear strength of the beams and hence these strengthened beams fail in flexure first or sometimes as flexure-shear failure.

3. MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Ordinary Portland cement of 53 grades conforming to IS: 12269 - 1987, Ground Granulated Blast furnace Slag (GGBS) conforming to IS: 12089 - 1987, fine aggregates of locally available river sand passing through 3.75 mm sieve and retained on 600 microns conforming of zone II of IS: 383 - 1970, coarse aggregate of crushed granite type passing through 20 mm sieve and retaining on 10 mm sieve conforming of IS: 383 - 1970 with portable water were used as the ingredients in concrete. Specific gravity and sieve analysis tests were conducted on cement, GGBS, fine and coarse aggregate and the results are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Properties of Aggregate, Cement and GGBS

Sl. No.	Properties of Aggregate and Cement	Values
1	Specific gravity of cement	3.14
2	Specific gravity of GGBS	2.83
3	Specific gravity of fine aggregate	2.60
4	Fineness modulus of fine aggregate	2.18
5	Specific gravity of coarse aggregate	2.74
6	Fineness modulus of coarse aggregate	6.66

The glass fibre reinforced polymer sheet of 1.5 mm thick was used for retrofitting of RC beams. The fibre orientation is unidirectional direction. The Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer sheet is available in 1.5 mm thickness. The fibre is oriented in unidirectional direction.

4. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

Initially, the properties of concrete were obtained by casting and testing of concrete specimens of cubes (150 mm x 150 mm x 150 mm) to determine the compressive strength, tensile strength and flexural strength respectively. The specimens were cast using various grades of concrete such as, M 40, Ordinary Portland cement, natural river sand and the coarse

aggregate crushed on maximum size of 12.5 mm were used and three numbers of specimens were cast and tested to take the average value at different curing period. The specimens were allowed for curing of different periods of 7, 14 and 28 days.

Flexural Behaviour of Control Beams

The static behaviour of beams includes studying the structural behaviour aspects such as deflection, crack propagation and ultimate load carrying capacity of the beam under monotonic conditions. Hence the beams were tested monotonically with simply supported boundary conditions. The crack pattern of beams is shown in Figure 1

Control Beam (M 20, M 40, and M 60) Grade

Figure 1 Crack Patterns of Control Beams of Varying Grades

These beams were loaded up to failure and deflections are measured for a load increment of

2.5 kN and these load deflection values were used as base values for other beams.

The concrete material properties for all the grades of concrete used in the beams are shown in Table 2

5. ANALYTICAL INVESTIGATIONS AND RESULT

Table 2 Concrete Material Properties

Grade of Concrete		Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	Young Modulus (E) (N/mm ²)	Poisson's Ratio (μ)
M20	RCC	28.40	2.51×10^4	0.186
M40	RCC	50.44	3.52×10^4	0.171
M60	RCC	73.56	4.32×10^4	0.160

5.1 MESHING

In Finite Element Analysis meshing requires for a model to analyse (Bathe, 1996). The reinforcement model is meshed using line elements so that the nodes of the line elements come exactly over the nodes of the solid elements which are later merged so that both the bar

elements and the concrete elements share the same node (William, 1975).

For beam generation total mesh model defined 3225 nodes and 2783 elements are required. The meshing of concrete is shown in Figure 2 and meshing of reinforcement is shown in Figure 3

Figure 2 Meshing of Concrete

Figure 3 Meshing of Reinforcement

5.2 LOADING AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The entire beam is used for the model. All beams are 125 mm wide, 250 mm deep and 3200 mm long simply supported at both ends. Figure 4.9 shows the two point loading system of beam with meshing.

Figure 4 Loading and Boundary Conditions

Table 3 Summary of Test Results

Beam Designation	Ultimate Load (kN)	Max. Deflection (mm)
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	Experimental	ANSYS	Experimental	ANSYS
M20CB	37.50	34.00	73.00	70.297
M20RB1	57.50	56.00	58.00	56.289
M20RB2	74.00	72.30	53.00	51.230
M20RB3	80.00	74.00	47.00	44.919
M40CB	104.00	103.50	61.50	56.835
M40RB1	118.50	112.00	44.50	44.659
M40RB2	123.00	120.00	43.50	41.846
M40RB3	136.50	126.00	41.00	40.273
M60CB	129.50	126.20	52.50	49.000
M60RB1	144.00	144.00	49.00	46.785
M60RB2	166.50	159.00	44.50	43.000
M60RB3	174.00	172.00	43.50	42.578

Fig 5 Experimental and Analytical Load Deflection Curves for Control Beam(M 20 Grade).

Fig 6 Experimental and Analytical Load Deflection Curves for Single Layer GFRP Sheet Retrofitted Beam (M20 Grade)

Fig 7 Experimental and Analytical Load Deflection Curves for Double Layer GFRP Sheet Retrofitted Beam (M20 Grade)

Fig 8
Experimental and Analytical Load Deflection Curves for Triple Layer GFRP Sheet Retrofitted Beam (M20 Grade)

Fig 9 Experimental and Analytical Load Deflection Curves for Control Beam (M40 Grade)

Fig 10
Experimental and Analytical Load Deflection Curves for Single Layer CFRP Sheet Retrofitted Beam (M40 Grade)

Table 4 Theoretical Load Deflection Values for M20 Beams

Sl.No.	Description	Load (kN)	Deflection (mm)
1.	Just before 1 st crack	10.18	1.04
2.	Position at which start of non-linearity stage	24.80	11.73
3.	Position at which yielding starts	31.00	22.89
4.	Point at which ultimate	32.80	61.29

Table 5 Theoretical Load Deflection Values for M40 Beams

Sl.No.	Description	Load(kN)	Deflection(mm)
1.	Justbefore1 st crack	12.64	1.16
2.	Positionatwhichstartofnon-linearitystage	60.16	10.23
3.	Positionatwhichyieldingstarts	74.00	13.00
4.	Pointatwhichultimate	91.40	58.70

Sl.No.	Description	Load(kN)	Deflection(mm)
1.	Justbefore1 st crack	14.62	1.00
2.	Positionatwhichstartofnon-linearitystage	79.50	12.80
3.	Positionatwhichyieldingstarts	108.50	23.93
4.	Pointatwhichultimate	120.00	50.00

Table6TheoreticalLoadDeflectionValuesforM60Beams

Figure 17 Experimental and Theoretical Load Deflection Curve of Control Beam (M20 Grade)

Figure 18 Experimental and Theoretical Load Deflection Curve of Control Beam (M40 Grade)

Figure 19 Experimental and Theoretical Load Deflection Curve of Control Beam (M60 Grade)

The comparison of experimental and theoretical analysis by section analysis for control beams shown that both are in good agreement with each other.

6. CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates that strengthening reinforced concrete beams with GFRP and CFRP sheets significantly enhances their load-carrying capacity. While deflections increase up to the yield stage of loading, they are notably reduced as the beams approach the ultimate load. Additionally, the strengthened beams exhibit a considerable reduction in crack width throughout all loading stages, along with a substantial delay in the initiation of the first crack. Crack pattern analysis further reveals that both the size and density of cracks are considerably lower in beams

reinforced with GFRP and CFRP compared to the unstrengthened control beams.

7. REFERENCES

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